

Bernt Isak Wærstad

Instrument design using machine learning and artificial intelligence

Colloquial Paper

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Abstract

The relationship between a performer and their instrument is an intricate one. To me, performing (together) with an instrument is as much about communication as it is about control. The instrument provides me with both resistance and inspiration in what I see essentially as a musical dialogue. There is something in this dialogue that feels fundamentally different to me when using digital instrument as opposed to traditional acoustic instruments. Digital instruments often tend to lack some of the response and resistance that is inherent in the acoustic instruments, while at the same time affording different modes of communication and interaction between the performer and the instrument. The purpose of this research project is to explore some digital instrument design strategies through analysis and exploration of those affordances. By using techniques more idiomatic to the digital domain like machine learning, artificial intelligence and computational creativity, I am seeking to both remedy the aforementioned shortcomings and facilitate new practices for performance and music production.

Keywords: Instrument design, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Computational Creativity

1. Introduction

I've been performing with a wide variety of digital musical instruments for the last 10 years. Most of them are hybrid instruments extending either my own guitar or traditional instruments played by other musicians. In either case, I often miss the tactile feel, haptic response and inherent resistance of acoustic instruments from my digital counterpart. These properties are important creative catalysers greatly affecting both the expressive capacity and the interaction between the instrument and the performer. This has led me on a search for resistance; some kind of dynamic response or feedback which can lead to new musical ideas or new ways of expressing them. I'm also on the search for contact; a way of connecting and communicating with my instruments, where a performance can be as much a musical dialogue between me and my instrument as me solely *controlling* or *playing* the instrument.

Instead of trying to copy or mimic the behaviour and physical properties of acoustic instruments, like many have through for instance exploring haptic response and resistance through sensors, motorised controllers, transducers, etc, I want to focus on the strengths of digital technology. By using techniques from machine learning and artificial intelligence in combination with generative techniques and algorithms from the field of computational creativity, I want to explore instrumental designs that are only possible with digital technology and research modes of instrumental response and resistance that are more idiomatic to the digital domain. The project will explore and develop new personal strategies for digital instrument design based around my own artistic expression. These strategies will be both used to expand my existing instruments and to design new responsive and autonomous instruments.

As of now, I see two main areas in which I imagine machine learning and AI can be put to interesting artistic use for the purpose of creating reactive, automatic and autonomous musical systems. The first area to explore is combining techniques from the fields of Machine Learning and Music Information Retrieval to create adaptive instruments. I obtained a lot of valuable experience in this field as a participant in the research project "Cross adaptive processing as musical intervention"¹ which led to new insights in working methods in designing and using adaptive instrument (Brandtsegg, Engum and Wærstad 2018). This project will continue the exploration started in the cross adaptive project by exploring these different MIR techniques can be combined with machine learning algorithms, though mostly in a more pure adaptive fashion (not cross).

The second area is related to idea of autonomy and artificial intelligence. Or perhaps artificial artistic identity would be a better term. I want to explore instrument designs with a form of "personality" which

¹ <http://crossadaptive.hf.ntnu.no/index.php/about-the-project/>

can develop and evolve over time. In a way, this is already a natural part of the way I design and interact with digital instruments. They are constantly evolving and I tend to think of the design process as constant cycle (fig. 1) where each round around the circle is another evolution. But it's not only the instruments that are changing. As with all musicians and the instruments they are using, I am also learning and adapting; evolving together with the instrument in a sort of symbiosis.

Figure 1. Cyclic instrument design process

I want to explore this relationship between me as a performer and my instruments over time further by designing autonomous instruments with a more explicit focus on its agency outside of a performance (what Bown et al. (2009) calls *memetic* agency). I'm interested to find out what kind of musical dialogues this relationship will produce and what place both me and the instruments will have in the larger context of music culture over time.

In this context, I also find it very relevant to explore how we perceive the machine and its output. What gives it a sense of agency and when do we interpret its actions as musical intent? In my early experiments, I found that even a simple smooth random walk produced a lot of, to me, meaningful musical ideas and initiatives. So introducing any kind of agency, even a random impulse, into the instruments are already giving me some sensation of autonomy from the machine, which directly affected my playing and encouraged a musical responses (a short excerpt can be heard at ²). This project will therefore also explore generative and algorithmic processes like Markov Chains, Lindenmayer Systems, Cellular Automata and GANs as means of giving artistic agency to the machine. Combined with different MIR techniques and reinforcement learning algorithms, these techniques will be used to explore strategies towards creating a performance AI, which in the long run would turn in to one or several autonomous systems with its own artistic identities.

2. Related work

The idea of having autonomous and interactive music systems are by no means new and this project are based on ideas from early algorithmic music systems like "Voyager" by George Lewis (Lewis 1999) and "Improsculpt" by Øyvind Brandtsegg (Brandtsegg 2001). More recent examples of relevant and inspiring projects are the machine improvisation system "PyOracle" (Surges and Dubnov 2013) by Greg Surges and Shlomo Dubnov, the AI performance system named "Tomomibot"³ by Andreas Dzialocha, Tomomi Adachi and Marcello Lussana and Agostini Di Scipio's interactive music system "Audible Eco-Systemic Interface (AESI)" (Scipio 2003).

Other relevant and related work includes the Fluid Corpus Manipulation project (FluCoMA)⁴, which are researching new ways of doing segmentation and classification of sounds and building different corpuses (Roma, Green and Tremblay 2019) and have recently also release a package of their tools for Max. Also in

² <https://soundcloud.com/mrbernts/a-smooth-random-walk>

³ <https://github.com/adzialocha/tomomibot>

⁴ <https://www.flucoma.org/>

Max is the MuBu toolbox⁵ from Ircam which includes tools for audio analysis, segmentation gesture recognition and a few machine learning algorithms more. Also related is Charles Martin, a loose collaborator on this project, who is researching how to do creative predictions using recurrent neural network and has developed an interactive musical prediction system (Martin and Torresen 2019). Hugo Scurto has done some relevant and interesting work with interactive reinforcement learning in the project “Co-Explorer” (Scurto et al. 2019). Im also following the development of generative machine learning algorithms like WaveNet, SampleRNN and more recently OpenAi’s Jukebox⁶ project (Dhariwal et al. 2020) to mention a few. Other important tools include Rebecca Fiebrink’s “Wekinator”⁷ and Sam Parke Wolfe’s encapsulation of the Rapid library as an Max MSP external, “RapidMax”⁸.

3. Method

So far, I’ve started this exploration by expanding and enhancing my existing digital musical instruments both as a solo performer and in the duo constellation *Seshen X Bernt*. In the latter, where all sounds are based around sound manipulations of Seshen’s voice, we have experimented with various segmentation and unsupervised classification techniques of a studio recorded corpus of acoustic vocal improvisations. This is an extension of the conceptual idea of using delays and live-sampling as a way of interacting with your past self. In our first tests we implemented a system where a sample of the real-time voice can upon activation be classified to pick out and play back similar voice samples. While our explorations have been quite rudimentary so far, it has already provided some interesting results and we plan on expanding this system to explore concatenative synthesis and musical mosaicing technique. We also want to explore adaptive processing techniques which could give back some of the control which Seshen has given up in this collaboration. The idea of redistributing control has already come up in our project “Touch the Voice!”, which is a collaboration with Bob Pritchard and Kiran Bhumber at University of British Columbia working with their bespoke RUBS (Responsive User Body Suite) touch sensor suite (Bhumber, Pritchard, Rode 2017) to include movement as part of our improvisation and let Seshen control certain processing parameters through the sensors on the suite. A video produced by the end of a weeklong workshop at UBC in Vancouver in November 2019 can be seen at⁹

As a solo performer, I have explored adaptive processing combined with machine learning to extend my existing performance practise using electric guitar with various preparation techniques and electronics. The first public performance showcasing this exploration was given at ICLI 2020 where both the performance and the new instrument system was named “Ghost Doctor Duplicate” (Wærstad 2020). To not lean too heavy on old habits, I chose a dogmatic approach for this performance focusing solely on digital effects and letting the adaptive system control all the processing.

As mentioned in the introduction, the nature of my work process is cycling rather than linear, where musical performance produces artistic reflection which forms the basis of the continued technical development leading to an improved instrument with which another musical performance can take place. I also see it as important that different modes of musical performance (rehearsal, concert, studio recording) are carried out to have varied foundation for reflection. Discussion and reflection with collaborators, colleagues and audiences will also be an important part of bringing this project forward.

4. Future work

Having started up in September 2019, the project is still in its infancy with “Touch the Voice!” being the first public outcome and the contributions to this conference the second. The project is formally of limited reach so far being tied to a 20% research position for one year, though applications have been made for further funding. The focus for the last months before the current ending date for the project on 31st of July will be to explore reinforcement learning and generative machine learning algorithms to start the process of building an autonomous performance system. I also plan on developing this project further with the goal of having it evolve into a more comprehensive artistic research project which would serve as the foundation for an artistic phd.

⁵ <http://ismm.ircam.fr/mubu/>

⁶ <https://openai.com/blog/jukebox/>

⁷ <http://www.wekinator.org>

⁸ <https://github.com/samparkewolfe/RapidMax>

⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=odrijbYc93M>

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